

Road Segmentation from Multi-Modal Imagery of Ilocos Norte using Mask-RCNN

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For Today

Introduction

Previous Studies

The Problem

Methodology

Results and Discussion

Conclusions and Recommendations

Introduction

What's known?

Road Segmentation contributes significantly to different areas.

- Routing (e.g. OSM, Google Maps, Waze)
- Urban Planning
- Traffic management
- Road Safety
- Identification of logistical schema for disaster stricken regions
- Hazard Mapping

What's known?

Road Segmentation is complex.

Hindrances such as trees, clouds and human artifacts.

Different types of roads on Different areas found in Different Countries

Different survey technologies also present challenges themselves.

What's known?

Various international efforts are being launched.

What's known?

Local Efforts

Map of possible users of DATOS AI Models

What's unknown?

- Local road datasets (images and annotations)
- Road Segmentation Model trained using the Ilocos Norte dataset and applied on different places in the Philippines
- Further exploration of multi-directional hillshaded LiDAR data and its combination with other data in road segmentation
- Implementation of Mask R-CNN for road segmentation in the Philippines

Our AIM

As a supplementary research to the current systems for the analysis of Philippine geographic data,

this study focuses on the segmentation of roads from combinations of LiDAR and Google Satellite imagery of the Philippines using Mask R-CNN.

Our Approach

Leveraging the region-based nature of Mask R-CNN,

we view this problem as a generalized instance segmentation instead of a semantic segmentation problem.

Our Approach

Specifically, we investigated

- **different annotations and augmentations**
- **scale evaluations and anchor scales**
- **dataset combinations and contrasts**
- **data preprocessing methods**
- **backbones**
- **model's generalization on different places in the Philippines**

For Today

What is this study all about?

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2 Previous Studies

DeepGlobe 2018: A Challenge to Parse the Earth through Satellite Images

Dataset Used

- DigitalGlobe Basemap +Vivid
 - 50cm/pixel resolution
- Captured over Thailand, Indonesia, and India
- Sample data uniformly between rural and urban areas
- Train-valid-test split: 70-15-15

*The urban morphology, illumination conditions, road density, and structure of street networks are significantly **diverse** among the samples.*

Semantic Segmentation Problem

- Labels generated are **pixel-based**
 - *Where all pixels belonging to the road are labeled, instead of labeling only the centerline*

Figure 2: Road labels are annotated on top of the satellite image patches, all taken from DeepGlobe Road Extraction Challenge dataset.

DeepGlobe 2018: A Challenge to Parse the Earth through Satellite Images

Model Used

- Modified version of DeepLab architecture with ResNet18 backbone and Focal Loss
- Data augmentation - simple rotation
- No post-processing for extracted road masks, only binarizing

Baseline IoU score: 0.545

Figure 4: Example results of our road extraction method with an *IoU* score of 0.545, with satellite image (left), extracted road mask (middle), and the ground truth (right).

DeepGlobe 2018: A Challenge to Parse the Earth through Satellite Images

Competition Results

Entry	IoU Score	CVPR Citations
D-LinkNet: LinkNet with Pretrained Encoder and Dilated Convolution for High Resolution Satellite Imagery Road Extraction	65.60	65
Fully Convolutional Network for Automatic Road Extraction From Satellite Imagery	64	24
Residual Inception Skip Network for Binary Segmentation	61.3	5
Road detection with EOSResUNet and post vectorizing algorithm	56	6
Semantic Binary Segmentation using Convolutional Networks without Decoders	60.60	8
Roadmap Generation using a Multi-Stage Ensemble of Deep Neural Networks with Smoothing-Based Optimization	60.58	1
Stacked U-Nets with Multi-Output for Road Extraction	60	24

SpaceNet: A Remote Sensing Dataset and Challenge Series

Dataset Used

- 30cm imagery
- Captured over Las Vegas, Paris, Shanghai, Khartoum, Moscow, Mumbai
- Labels for each roadway are hand drawn, and include metadata features such as surface type, road type (primary, secondary, highway, etc.), and number of lanes.
- Train-valid-test split: 60-20-20

*Specifically designed as **open source routing tools** designed to enable the creation of routable road networks, a labeling schema based on OpenStreetMap (OSM) guidelines was established to ensure ground truth that would be usable by open source routing tools.*

Figure 2: 400m SpaceNet chip of Las Vegas. Left: SpaceNet GeoJSON road label. Right: RGB image overlaid with road centerlines (orange).

SpaceNet: A Remote Sensing Dataset and Challenge Series

First Image: Sample XD_XD prediction over Dar Es Salaam, with **ground truth in blue** and **predictions in yellow**; the time-weighted APLS score for this chip is 0.64. **Second Image:** Sample XD_XD prediction over Moscow; despite the fact that portions of Moscow are in the training set, **the snow and shadows sometimes complicate road extraction**, and the time-weighted APLS score for this chip is only 0.37. **Third Image:** Sample XD_XD prediction over San Juan — APLS = 0.78. **Fourth Image:** Sample XD_XD prediction over Mumbai — APLS = 0.61.

Detecting Roads from Satellite Imagery in the Developing World

Y. Nachmany, H. Alemohammad

CVPR 2019

We review state-of-the-art models for road detection using satellite imagery, and compare predictions of two models (one trained in Las Vegas, USA and another in Khartoum, Sudan) in Khartoum. This comparison shows the need for regionally trained models using local training data.

Figure 4. Prediction results in Khartoum for four different scenes. Top: input imagery, middle: prediction results (shaded) from the model trained in Las Vegas overlaid with labels (red lines) on top of the input imagery, bottom: prediction results (shaded) from the model trained in Khartoum overlaid with labels (red lines) on top of the input imagery.

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The Problem

Vision Tasks

Semantic Segmentation

GRASS, CAT,
TREE, SKY

No objects, just pixels

Classification + Localization

CAT

Single Object

Object Detection

DOG, DOG, CAT

Multiple Object

Instance Segmentation

DOG, DOG, CAT

This image is CC0 public domain

Source: CS231n Convolutional Neural Networks

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Source: CS231n Convolutional Neural Networks

Generalizing Instance Segmentation

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Methodology

Environment

GeForce GTX TITAN X
Memory Clock Rate(GHz): 1.076
Total Memory: 12GB

Source: Amazon

Seagate External Drive
Total Memory: 4TB

Source: scan.co.uk

Some Technologies Used

imageio

Generalizing Instance Segmentation

Overview of the Methodology

Overview of the Methodology

Datasets

Google Satellite Images

- QGIS basemap (through XYZ connection)
- 1:1m Layer Resolution
- Saved as Geotiff (or .tif)
 - contains info on:
 1. Spatial Extent
(What area does this dataset cover?)
 2. Coordinate Reference System
(What spatial projection / coordinate reference system is used to store the data?)
 3. Resolution
(What area on the ground does each pixel cover?)
 4. no data

Datasets

LiDAR data

DOST Nationwide Hazard Mapping of the Philippines Using LiDAR (PHIL-LiDAR 1 and 2) Program

* Accessed through **LiPAD** (LiDAR Portal for Archiving and Distribution)

Datasets

Raw LiDAR

225 degrees

270 degrees

315 degrees

360 degrees

Resulting
multi-directional
hillshaded image

Overview of the Methodology

Dataset Preparation

Google Satellite Images

Example Tiles:

Dataset Preparation

Multi-directional Hillshaded LiDAR Data

Example Tiles:

Dataset Preparation

Train, Valid and Test Splits

	No. of Samples	No. of Positive Samples	No. of Negative Samples
Train	1,400	405 (28.93%)	995 (71.07%)
Valid	400	102 (25.5%)	298 (74.5%)
Test	200	49 (24.5%)	151 (75.5%)
Total	2,000		

Not augmented

Dataset Preparation

Data Augmentation

Original Image

Rotation (-90 deg)

Rotation (90 deg)

Rotation (180 deg)

Flip Left-Right

**Flip Left-Right,
Rotation (-90 deg)**

**Flip Right-Left
Rotation (90 deg)**

Flip Up-Down

Dataset Preparation

Train, Valid and Test Splits

	No. of Samples	No. of Positive Samples	No. of Negative Samples
Train	11,200	3 480 (31.07%)	7 720 (68.93%)
Valid	400	102 (25.5%)	298 (74.5%)
Test	200	49 (24.5%)	151 (75.5%)
Total	11,800		

Augmented

Overview of the Methodology

Mask R-CNN

(Mask Region-based Convolutional Neural Network)

Mini-Flow:

- 1. How does the computer interpret images?**
2. Overview of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)
3. Overview of the R-CNN Family
4. Conceptual Mask R-CNN
5. Mask R-CNN Implementation
6. Transfer Learning

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Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)

Source: Udacity

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

Source: Udacity

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

Source: Udacity

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Vision Tasks

Semantic Segmentation

GRASS, CAT,
TREE, SKY

No objects, just pixels

Instance Segmentation

DOG, DOG, CAT

Source: CS231n Convolutional Neural Networks

R-CNN

R-CNN: *Regions with CNN features*

Source: Rich feature hierarchies for accurate object detection and semantic segmentation
Tech report (v5)

R-CNN Family

Object Detection

Source: Lilian Weng
Instance Segmentation

UP Computer Vision and Machine Intelligence Laboratory

Mini-Flow:

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Mask R-CNN

(Mask Region-based Convolutional Neural Network)

Source: Mask R-CNN paper

Mask R-CNN Mask Loss

Mask R-CNN Bounding Box Loss

Mask R-CNN Class Loss

Mask R-CNN

Source: Mask R-CNN, Kaiming He, Facebook, ICCV2017

Feature Pyramid Network (FPN)

- used for detecting objects at different scales
- skip connections are used such that all levels will be semantically strong

(d) Feature Pyramid Network

Source: FPN paper

Mask R-CNN

Losses

$$\text{Overall Loss} = L_{\text{RPN BBox}} + L_{\text{RPN Class}} + L_{\text{Mask R-CNN BBox}} + L_{\text{Mask R-CNN Class}} + L_{\text{Mask R-CNN Mask}}$$

● RPN Losses

○ $L_{\text{RPN BBox}}$

- computed from the tuple of true bounding-box regression

targets for class u , $v = (v^x, v^y, v^w, v^h)$ and a

predicted tuple for class u , $t^u = (t^u_x, t^u_y, t^u_w, t^u_h)$,

- robust L1 loss that is less sensitive to outliers than the L2 loss used in R-CNN

$$L_{\text{loc}}(t^u, v) = \sum_{i \in \{x, y, w, h\}} \text{smooth}_{L_1}(t_i^u - v_i), \quad (2)$$

in which

$$\text{smooth}_{L_1}(x) = \begin{cases} 0.5x^2 & \text{if } |x| < 1 \\ |x| - 0.5 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Source: Fast R-CNN paper

Mask R-CNN

Losses

$$\text{Overall Loss} = L_{\text{RPN BBox}} + L_{\text{RPN Class}} + L_{\text{Mask R-CNN BBox}} + L_{\text{Mask R-CNN Class}} + L_{\text{Mask R-CNN Mask}}$$

● RPN Losses

○ $L_{\text{RPN Class}}$

- Sparse Categorical Entropy
 - The difference between Categorical and Sparse Categorical Entropy is in the representation
 - saves memory when the label is sparse (the number of classes is very large)

Difference:

```
y_true = [[0, 0, 1],  
          [1, 0, 0],  
          [0, 0, 1]]
```

Will become:

```
y_true_one_hot = [2, 0, 2]
```

Source: cwiki.apache.org

Mask R-CNN

Losses

$$\text{Overall Loss} = L_{\text{RPN BBox}} + L_{\text{RPN Class}} + L_{\text{Mask R-CNN BBox}} + L_{\text{Mask R-CNN Class}} + L_{\text{Mask R-CNN Mask}}$$

Mask R-CNN Losses

- $L_{\text{Mask R-CNN BBox}}$ (same with $L_{\text{RPN BBox}}$)
- $L_{\text{Mask R-CNN Class}}$
 - Sparse Softmax Cross Entropy with Logits
- $L_{\text{Mask R-CNN Mask}}$
 - Average Binary Cross Entropy

probabilities = sigmoid(logits)
loss = BCE(probabilities, labels)

Source: Raul Gomez

For more detailed explanations

Mask R-CNN Unmasked by Fractal Analytics' Machine-vision team

<https://medium.com/@fractaldle>

Understanding Feature Pyramid Networks for object detection (FPN) by Jonathan Hui

https://medium.com/@jonathan_hui

Mini-Flow:

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6. Transfer Learning

Mask R-CNN

 [matterport / Mask_RCNN](#)

Mask R-CNN for object detection and instance segmentation on Keras and TensorFlow

 [View license](#)

 8.5k forks

Known deviations from the paper:

- Image Resizing
 - Resizing of image to the same size while preserving aspect ratio
- Bounding boxes
 - Bounding boxes are generated on the fly via the masks (Simplifies image augmentation)
- Learning Rate
 - Paper: 0.02
 - Too high; may often cause weight explosion (especially using a small batch size)
 - Use of gradient clipping

Mask R-CNN

Projects using Matterport's Mask R-CNN

4K Video Demo by Karol Majek.

Splash of Color. A blog post explaining how to train this model from scratch and use it to implement a color splash effect.

Mask R-CNN

Projects using Matterport's Mask R-CNN

Segmenting Nuclei in Microscopy Images.
Built for the 2018 Data Science Bowl

GRASS GIS Addon to generate vector masks from geospatial imagery. Based on a Master's thesis by Ondřej Pešek.

Mini-Flow:

1. How does the computer interpret images?
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Transfer Learning

Transfer Learning

Using what other models have learned on a new application.

MS Coco

COCO is a large-scale object detection, segmentation, and captioning dataset. COCO has several features:

- ✓ Object segmentation
- ✓ Recognition in context
- ✓ Superpixel stuff segmentation
- ✓ 330K images (>200K labeled)
- ✓ 1.5 million object instances
- ✓ 80 object categories
- ✓ 91 stuff categories
- ✓ 5 captions per image
- ✓ 250,000 people with keypoints

Collaborators

- Tsung-Yi Lin Google Brain
- Genevieve Patterson MSR, Trash TV
- Matteo R. Ronchi Caltech
- Yin Cui Google
- Michael Maire TTI-Chicago
- Serge Belongie Cornell Tech
- Lubomir Bourdev WaveOne, Inc.
- Ross Girshick FAIR
- James Hays Georgia Tech
- Pietro Perona Caltech
- Deva Ramanan CMU
- Larry Zitnick FAIR
- Piotr Dollár FAIR

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Overview of the Methodology

Binary Masking

Black Tile

**Predicted Image
with Instances**

***3 Channels**

**Convert to
Grayscale**

***1 Channel**

**Convert non-zero
areas to white**

Evaluation Metrics

Dice Score

(also known as Dice Similarity Coefficient/Sorensen-Dice Coefficient)

Set Form:

$$DSC = \frac{2|X \cap Y|}{|X| + |Y|}$$

Boolean Form:

$$DSC = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN}$$

Image Source: Erik Tiu

Intersection over Union

(also known as Jaccard Index)

Set Form:

$$IoU = \frac{|X \cap Y|}{|X \cup Y|}$$

Boolean Form:

$$IoU = \frac{TP}{TP + FP + FN}$$

Image Source: Erik Tiu

where

X, Y - can either be the actual and predicted images

TP (True Positive) - When a data point is classified as a positive example and it is actually a positive example

FP (False Positive) - When a data point is classified as a positive example but it is actually a negative example

FN (False Negative) - When a data point is classified as a negative example but it is actually a positive example

Evaluation Metrics

Relationship between Dice Score and Intersection over Union

$$DSC = \frac{2TP}{2TP + FP + FN}$$

$$IoU = \frac{TP}{TP + FP + FN}$$

$$DSC = \frac{TP}{TP + \frac{1}{2}FP + \frac{1}{2}FN}$$

$$IoU \leq DSC$$

where

X, Y - can either be the actual and predicted images

TP (True Positive) - When a data point is classified as a positive example and it is actually a positive example

FP (False Positive) - When a data point is classified as a positive example but it is actually a negative example

FN (False Negative) - When a data point is classified as a negative example but it is actually a positive example

Overview of the Methodology

Experiments

(6) Six Sets of Experiments

1. Annotations and Augmentations
2. Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales
3. Data Combinations and Contrasts
4. Data Preprocessing
5. Backbones
6. Different Places in the Philippines

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

Whole

Segmented

Piece

Different Polygonal Annotations

Annotations and Augmentations

Data Augmentation

Original Image

Rotation (-90 deg)

Rotation (90 deg)

Rotation (180 deg)

Flip Left-Right

**Flip Left-Right,
Rotation (-90 deg)**

**Flip Right-Left
Rotation (90 deg)**

Flip Up-Down

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

To decide we look at the:

1. Loss Behavior

- tells how the model learns
- considers the:
 - loss oscillation
 - gap and trend
 - data augmentation effect
 - loss contributions to the overall loss

2. Evaluation

- mean Dice (mDice) and mean IoU (mIoU) for unaugmented and augmented data

Set 2: Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Set 2: Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Scale Evaluations

- evaluating on different image sizes or resolutions
- VGG Paper shows increase in performance using different scales in CNNs

Single-Scale Evaluations

- train and test images has the same input size

Multi-Scale Evaluations

- done through scale jittering (a data augmentation technique which do jittering of the resolution rather than changing the scale.
- train and/or test images can both have multiple image sizes

What does resizing do to images?

Resizing the images into a higher resolution takes more pixels to represent a single pixel.

Set 2: Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Anchor Scales and Aspect Ratio

Example:

Anchor Scales:

128x128, 256x256, 512,512

Aspect Ratio (H:W):

1:1, 1:2, 2:1

Set 2: Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

ICE BREAKER

FINDING

Ma'am Rae

bit.ly/FindMaamRae

Set 2: Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

What is the relationship between an image size and anchor scales?

When we change the image size, the pixels covering the original pixel size change and thus, the size of the objects we wanted the anchors to enclose also change.

Bigger objects need larger scales of anchors,
Smaller objects need smaller scales of anchors.

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

image size: 256x256

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

Default: 32, 64, 128, 256, 512

image size: 256x256

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

16, 32, 64, 192, 224

Height vs. Width of True Bounding Boxes

% Frequency for Groupings of Bounding Boxes' Width Sizes

% Frequency for Groupings of Bounding Boxes' Height Sizes

image size: 256x256

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

32, 64, 128, 192, 256

image size: 256x256

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

image size: 256x256

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

image size: 512x512

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

Default: 32, 64, 128, 256, 512

image size: 512x512

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

64, 128, 192, 384, 512

image size: 512x512

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

image size: 512x512

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

Default: 32, 64, 128, 256, 512

image size: 1024x1024 (padded 800x800)

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Explore True Bounding Box Sizes

64, 128, 192, 384, 1024

image size: 1024x1024 (padded 800x800)

Experiment Setups:

Train Image Size (pixels)	Test Image Size (pixels)	Anchor Scales
256	256	16, 32, 64, 192, 224
		32, 64, 128, 192, 256
		32, 64, 128, 256, 512
512	512	64, 128, 192, 384, 512
		32, 64, 128, 256, 512
1024	1024	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
		64, 128, 192, 384, 1024

*Aspect ratio kept at (0.5, 1, 2)

Single-Scale Evaluation

Experiment Setups:

Train Image Size (pixels)	Test Image Sizes (pixels)	Anchor Scales
256	256, 384, 448	16, 32, 64, 192, 224
	384, 448, 512	16, 32, 64, 192, 224
	256, 384, 448	32, 64, 128, 192, 256
	384, 448, 512	32, 64, 128, 192, 256
	256, 384, 448	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
	384, 448, 512	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
512	384, 448, 512	64, 128, 192, 384, 512
	256, 448, 512	64, 128, 192, 384, 512
	256, 384, 448	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
	384, 448, 512	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
1024	384, 448, 512	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
	448, 512, 1024	32, 64, 128, 256, 512
	384, 448, 1024	64, 128, 192, 384, 1024
	448, 512, 1024	64, 128, 192, 384, 1024

*Aspect ratio kept at (0.5, 1, 2)

Multi-Scale Evaluation

Set 3: Data Combinations and Contrasts

Set 3:

Data Combinations and Contrasts

Satelite Image

Multi-directional Hillshaded LiDAR

Soft Light

Lighten

Dodge

Addition

Darken

Multiply

Hard Light

Diference

Subtract

Grain Extract

Grain Merge

Divide

Raw Images

Blended Images

Set 3:

Data Combinations and Contrasts

Satellite Images

Combined Satellite Images with LiDAR

LiDAR

0

15

25

35

Set 3: Data Combinations and Contrasts

Experiment Setup:

Dataset	Contrast
Satellite Image	0
	15
	25
	35
Combined Satellite Images with LiDAR	0
	15
	35
LiDAR	0

Set 4: Data Preprocessing

Set 4: Data Preprocessing Methods

Preprocessing

- means transforming the data before feeding to the network or algorithm
- studies show preprocessing data than using the raw data leads to better performance (such as learning and in evaluation)

Mean Pixel Subtraction

- other names: per-pixel mean subtraction, mean normalization
- serves to "center" the data
- "the brightness of the whole training set is normalized with respect to each dimension"

Formula: Given an image with a channel X :

$$X = X - \mu \quad \text{where } \mu \text{ is the mean pixel of that channel}$$

How did we compute the mean pixel for our dataset?

- we sum all of the pixel values then divided by the total number of pixels
- we do that per channel (R, G, B) of the whole training set

Set 4:

Data Preprocessing Methods

Mean Pixel Subtraction

R = 123.7 G = 116.5 B = 103.9
ImageNet (Default)

R = 0 G = 0 B = 0
Original

R = 68.12 G = 75.37 B = 71.57
Dataset's

Set 4: Data Preprocessing Methods

Experiment Setup:

Dataset	Mean Pixel Value
ImageNet (Default)	123.7, 116.8, 103.9
None	0, 0, 0
Ilocos Norte Dataset	68.12, 75.37, 71.57

Set 5: Backbones

Set 5:

Backbones

Where do backbones fit in Mask R-CNN?

Recall:

Bottom-Up
Pathway

(d) Feature Pyramid Network

Source: FPN paper

Set 5: Backbones

Backbones

- usually refers to the feature extractor which takes images as input
ex: ResNets, Inception, VGG

Residual Nets (ResNets)

- made to address the problem of worsening performance of deep neural networks
 - addressing the vanishing gradient problem
- made up of **residual blocks**

Source: Deep Residual Networks for Image Recognition Paper

Set 5:

Backbones

Plain

Conv Layers

ResNet

Source: Deep Residual Networks for Image Recognition Paper

Set 5:

Backbones

Plain

Pooling Layers

ResNet

Source: Deep Residual Networks for Image Recognition Paper

Set 5: Backbones

Experiment Setup:

Backbone

ResNet101

ResNet50

Set 6: Different Places in the Philippines

Set 6: Different Places in the Philippines

Ilocos Norte

- model was trained on this area because of its mixed topography

Set 6: Different Places in the Philippines

Metro Manila

- urbanized area with diverse road patterns

Set 6: Different Places in the Philippines

Bohol

- mountainous area with mostly curved or zigzag roads

Set 6: Different Places in the Philippines

South Cotabato

- rural area with flat terrain, mostly surrounded by agricultural crops
- narrow and straight roads

For Today

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Methodology

Previous Studies

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The Problem

Conclusions and Recommendations

5

Results and Discussion

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

Set 1:

Annotations and Augmentations

Loss Behavior

(a) Whole

(b) Segmented

(c) Piece

Overall Losses

Set 1:

Annotations and Augmentations

Loss Contribution

Breakdown of Overall Losses when Augmentation is applied. **A** shows the loss breakdown for the three annotations until 30 epochs. **B** considers the contribution of different losses on the epoch with the least overall validation loss.

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

Evaluations

Annotation	mDice	mIoU
not augmented		
whole	68.71	61.21
segmented	68.27	60.88
piece	71.47	63.41
augmented		
whole	69.41	61.66
segmented	69.11	61.48
piece	72.1	63.94

Performance Results on Different Annotations

Qualitatively

image

ground truth

Dice: 76.14

Dice: 76.18

Dice: 81.56

Dice: 80.5

Dice: 70.26

Dice: 84.40

(a) Whole

(b) Segmented

(c) Piece

Mask Results from Different Annotations

Qualitatively

Mask Results using Whole Annotation

Set 1:

Annotations and Augmentations

Qualitatively

Mask Results using Segmented Annotation

Qualitatively

Mask Results using Piece Annotation

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

WE FOUND THAT

Piece Annotation is the most favorable.

- ✓ Selection is heavily weighted by the Dice Score and IoU results
- ✓ Loss behavior is most of the time in between the performance of the Whole and Segmented annotation and shows opportunity for further improvement for tuning.
- ✓ Qualitative results also show that it introduces more correct parts and the introduction of the incorrect parts are more subtle

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

WE FOUND THAT

Specifically for Mask R-CNN, as a region-based convolutional network, using different polygonal annotations have a significant impact on the behavior of the losses (loss oscillations, gaps and trends, and loss contributions) and evaluations even if they cover the same area.

WE FOUND THAT

Generally, the choice of architecture influence the varying effects of using different annotations, especially for supervised learning methods

Source: MissingLink.ai

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

CVPR 2019

Comparing the Effects of Annotation Type on Machine Learning Detection Performance

J.F Mullen Jr, F.R Tanner, P.A Sallee

“Selection of annotation technique is a tradeoff between time to annotate and accuracy of the annotation. When annotating a dataset for machine object recognition algorithms, researchers may not know the most advantageous method of annotation for their experiments”

Garbage in, Garbage out.
Annotation is an issue in supervised learning.

Figure 1. Images of targets identified with polygons (left), bounding boxes (middle), and target centroid (right). Image from [28]. Images courtesy of the U.S. Geological Survey.

WE FOUND THAT

Loss bounding box contributions matches human intuition.

Breakdown of Overall Losses when Augmentation is applied. **A** shows the loss breakdown for the three annotations until 30 epochs. **B** considers the contribution of different losses on the epoch with the least overall validation loss.

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

WE FOUND THAT

Even if the bounding box losses contributes mainly on the overall loss, we were still able to get as high as a dice score of 72.1 and an IoU of 63.94.

Set 1:

Annotations and Augmentations

Looking further

Predicted Bounding Boxes and Masks on images containing few roads (top) and various connected roads (bottom).

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

Our Study has limitations.

- The three different annotations may have pixel level differences but they were created such that they cover the same area.
- These polygonal annotations were investigated with roads as objects -- connected and the boundaries are hard to determine.

Source: Matterport

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

Our Study has limitations.

- These polygonal annotations were only investigated in Mask R-CNN, which is one type of the many region-based architecture and techniques for segmentation.
- This does not compare polygonal annotations to other forms of annotations -- binary mask annotation, bounding box annotation, donut annotation, etc.-- and thus, does not mean polygonal annotation is superior to other kinds of annotation.

Set 2: Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Train Image Size (pixels)	Test Image Size (pixels)	Anchor Scales	mDice	mIoU
256	256	16, 32, 64, 192, 224	64.79	58.41
		32, 64, 128, 192, 256	68.57	61.13
		32, 64, 128, 256, 512	63.93	57.81
512	512	64, 128, 192, 384, 512	62.29	56.74
		32, 64, 128, 256, 512	64.86	58.47
1024	1024	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	72.1	63.94
		64, 128, 192, 384, 1024	68.16	60.82
*Aspect ratio kept at (0.5, 1, 2)				

Single-Scale Evaluations at Different Anchor Scales

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Train Image Size (pixels)	Test Image Sizes (pixels)	Anchor Scales	mDice	mIoU
256	256, 384, 448	16, 32, 64, 192, 224	61.64	56.28
	384, 448, 512	16, 32, 64, 192, 224	59.38	54.83
	256, 384, 448	32, 64, 128, 192, 256	65.51	58.95
	384, 448, 512	32, 64, 128, 192, 256	63.07	57.26
	256, 384, 448	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	60.78	55.79
	384, 448, 512	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	59.95	54.62
512	384, 448, 512	64, 128, 192, 384, 512	63.31	57.42
	256, 448, 512	64, 128, 192, 384, 512	61.67	56.36
	256, 384, 448	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	69.08	61.59
	384, 448, 512	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	68.23	59.97
1024	384, 448, 512	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	66.63	59.5
	448, 512, 1024	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	68.96	61.36
	384, 448, 1024	64, 128, 192, 384, 1024	68.67	61.2
	448, 512, 1024	64, 128, 192, 384, 1024	68.49	60.89

*Aspect ratio kept at (0.5, 1, 2)

Multi-Scale Evaluations at Different Anchor Scales

Set 2: Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

WE FOUND THAT

Increasing the resolution and Scale Jittering still has a place for Mask R-CNN since it helped increase the performance but the effect is not consistent.

Set 2: Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

WE FOUND THAT

The selection of anchor scales is very significant as it causes big disruptions on the results.

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Train Image Size (pixels)	Test Image Size (pixels)	Anchor Scales	mDice	mIoU
256	256	16, 32, 64, 192, 224	64.79	58.41
		32, 64, 128, 192, 256	68.57	61.13
		32, 64, 128, 256, 512	63.93	57.81

← **Smaller objects**

← **Exploration of True BBoxes**

← **Default**

*Aspect ratio kept at (0.5, 1, 2)

The exploration of True BBoxes helped.

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Train Image Size (pixels)	Test Image Size (pixels)	Anchor Scales	mDice	mIoU
512	512	64, 128, 192, 384, 512	62.29	56.74
		32, 64, 128, 256, 512	64.86	58.47

← Exploration of True BBoxes

← Default

*Aspect ratio kept at (0.5, 1, 2)

Single-Scale Evaluations at Different Anchor Scales

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Train Image Size (pixels)	Test Image Size (pixels)	Anchor Scales	mDice	mIoU	
1024	1024	32, 64, 128, 256, 512	72.1	63.94	← Default
		64, 128, 192, 384, 1024	68.16	60.82	← Exploration of True BBoxes

*Aspect ratio kept at (0.5, 1, 2)

Single-Scale Evaluations at Different Anchor Scales

Set 2:

Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Potential Explanation includes

256

512

1024

Set 2: Scale Evaluations and Anchor Scales

Potential Explanation includes

1. As the resolution goes up, the distribution of bounding boxes became more and more varied.
2. The number of chosen anchor scales cannot accommodate other objects.
3. Our approach of exploring /visualizing the size of objects is also a factor.
4. The number of anchor scales used can also contribute.

Set 3: Data Combinations and Contrasts

Dataset	contrast	mDice	mIoU
Satellite Image	0	72.1	63.94
	15	74.07	65.61
	25	70.06	62.22
	35	70.07	62.27
Combined Satellite Images with LiDAR	0	71.21	63.2
	15	70.79	62.83
	35	65.72	59.05
LiDAR	0	53.05	50.94

Evaluations on Different Datasets and Contrasts

Dataset	contrast	mDice	mIoU
Satellite Image	0	72.1	63.94
	15	74.07	65.61
	25	70.06	62.22
	35	70.07	62.27
Combined Satellite Images with LiDAR	0	71.21	63.2
	15	70.79	62.83
	35	65.72	59.05
LiDAR	0	53.05	50.94

Evaluations on Different Datasets and Contrasts

Set 3:

Data Combinations and Contrasts

Set 3:

Data Combinations and Contrasts

Dataset	contrast	mDice	mIoU
Satellite Image	0	72.1	63.94
	15	74.07	65.61
	25	70.06	62.22
	35	70.07	62.27
Combined Satellite Images with LiDAR	0	71.21	63.2
	15	70.79	62.83
	35	65.72	59.05
LiDAR	0	53.05	50.94

Evaluations on Different Datasets and Contrasts

Set 3:

Data Combinations and Contrasts

Set 3: Data Combinations and Contrasts

WE FOUND THAT

When using the Satellite Images, increasing the image contrast at some point increases the performance.

Set 3: Data Combinations and Contrasts

WE FOUND THAT

Combining the Multidirectional Hillshaded LiDAR with Satellite Images helped increase the performance relative to using LiDAR data alone.

Set 3: Data Combinations and Contrasts

WE FOUND THAT

Multidirectional Hillshaded LiDAR images alone helps to see roads without hindrances; however, it segments roads way worse than using Satellite images or when combined.

Set 3:

Data Combinations and Contrasts

Original Image

LiDAR

Set 3: Data Combinations and Contrasts

WE FOUND THAT

Multidirectional Hillshaded LiDAR images specialize in some areas only.

- **favorable** (highways)
- **almost cannot be traced** (cities, mountains, near shore, near fields)
- **cannot be traced** (road bridges)

Set 3:

Data Combinations and Contrasts

favorable

Original Image

LiDAR

highways

Set 3:

Data Combinations and Contrasts

Almost cannot be traced

Original Image

LiDAR

cities

mountains

Set 3:

Data Combinations and Contrasts

Almost cannot be traced

Original Image

LiDAR

near shore

near fields

Set 3: Data Combinations and Contrasts

Cannot be traced

road bridges

Set 3: Data Combinations and Contrasts

Our Study has limitations.

- For Satellite Images combined with LiDAR data,
 - **The satellite and LiDAR surveys' capture dates are different.**
 - This is **normal** since satellites and LiDAR surveys have **different visiting times**
 - We did not check in detail each of the images regarding the differences in the capture times.
 - implication: in some places, roads may or may not have been added or removed.
- Before our data came to our hands, there was also internal preprocessing that created the data that may have their own limitations.

Set 3:

Data Combinations and Contrasts

**Example of
Satellite
Capturing**

Source: PHL-MicroSat

**UP Computer Vision and Machine
Intelligence Laboratory**

Set 4: Data Preprocessing

Set 4: Data Preprocessing Methods

Dataset	Mean Pixel Value	mDice	mIoU
ImageNet (Default)	123.7, 116.8, 103.9	74.07	65.61
None	0, 0, 0	72.86	64.55
Ilocos Norte Dataset	68.12, 75.37, 71.57	73.27	64.94

Evaluations on Different Mean Pixel Values of Datasets for Mean Pixel Subtraction

Dataset	Mean Pixel Value	mDice	mIoU
ImageNet (Default)	123.7, 116.8, 103.9	74.07	65.61
None	0, 0, 0	72.86	64.55
Ilocos Norte Dataset	68.12, 75.37, 71.57	73.27	64.94

Evaluations on Different Mean Pixel Values of Datasets for Mean Pixel Subtraction

Set 4: Data Preprocessing Methods

WE FOUND THAT

Using our dataset mean pixel value yields better performance than without doing data preprocessing at all.

Dataset	Mean Pixel Value	mDice	mIoU
ImageNet (Default)	123.7, 116.8, 103.9	74.07	65.61
None	0, 0, 0	72.86	64.55
Ilocos Norte Dataset	68.12, 75.37, 71.57	73.27	64.94

Evaluations on Different Mean Pixel Values of Datasets for Mean Pixel Subtraction

Set 4: Data Preprocessing Methods

WE FOUND THAT

Using mean pixel values from a larger dataset, like ImageNet, yields a better result than using our own dataset's mean pixel values.

Set 4: Data Preprocessing Methods

ImageNet is an ongoing research effort to provide researchers around the world an easily accessible image database.

Senior Researchers:

- Prof. Li Fei-Fei, PI, Stanford University
- Prof. Jia Deng, Princeton University
- Prof. Olga Russakovsky, Princeton University
- Prof. Alex Berg, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill
- Prof. Kai Li, Princeton University

(As of April 30, 2010)

Total number of images:
14,197,122

Number of images with bounding box annotations:
1,034,908

more info in <http://image-net.org/>

UP Computer Vision and Machine Intelligence Laboratory

Set 5: Backbones

Set 5: Backbones

Backbone	mDice	mIoU
ResNet101	74.07	65.61
ResNet50	64.60	72.93

Evaluations on Different Backbones

Set 5: Backbones

WE FOUND THAT

The deeper the residual network, the better the performance we have.

In most studies or architectures, ResNet101 also performed better.

method	top-1 err.	top-5 err.
VGG [41] (ILSVRC'14)	-	8.43 [†]
GoogLeNet [44] (ILSVRC'14)	-	7.89
VGG [41] (v5)	24.4	7.1
PReLU-net [13]	21.59	5.71
BN-inception [16]	21.99	5.81
ResNet-34 B	21.84	5.71
ResNet-34 C	21.53	5.60
ResNet-50	20.74	5.25
ResNet-101	19.87	4.60
ResNet-152	19.38	4.49

Table 4. Error rates (%) of **single-model** results on the ImageNet validation set (except [†] reported on the test set).

<i>net-depth-features</i>	AP	AP ₅₀	AP ₇₅
ResNet-50-C4	30.3	51.2	31.5
ResNet-101-C4	32.7	54.2	34.3
ResNet-50-FPN	33.6	55.2	35.3
ResNet-101-FPN	35.4	57.3	37.5
ResNeXt-101-FPN	36.7	59.5	38.9

(a) **Backbone Architecture:** Better backbones bring expected gains: deeper networks do better, FPN outperforms C4 features, and ResNeXt improves on ResNet.

Network	block4	block5	block6	block7
ResNet-50	64.81	72.14	74.29	73.88
ResNet-101	68.39	73.21	75.34	75.76

Table 2. Going deeper with atrous convolution when employing ResNet-50 and ResNet-101 with different number of cascaded blocks at *output_stride* = 16. Network structures ‘block4’, ‘block5’, ‘block6’, and ‘block7’ add extra 0, 1, 2, 3 cascaded modules respectively. The performance is generally improved by adopting more cascaded blocks.

Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition
 Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, Jian Sun

Mask R-CNN
 Kaiming He, Georgia Gkioxari, Piotr Dollar, Ross Girshick

Rethinking Atrous Convolution for Semantic Image Segmentation (DeepLab)
 Liang-Chieh Chen, George Papandreou, Florian Schroff, Hartwig Adam

Set 6: Different Places in the Philippines

Test Set	mDice	mIoU
Ilocos Norte	74.07	65.61
Metro Manila	72.93	61.25
Bohol	81.86	72.98
South Cotabato	81.85	72.92

Evaluations on Different Test Sets

Set 6: Different Places in the Philippines

WE FOUND THAT

In the Ilocos Norte dataset, it performs:

- **favorably** from separate roads to few connected roads
 - **unfavorably** on several connected roads (mostly in cities)
 - **confused** on several road looking structures
- no matter what the kind of area is considered.

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

favorably

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

Original Image

Ground Truth

Predicted Mask

unfavorably

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

Original Image

Predicted Mask

river artifacts,
dried river parts

water
boundaries

almost dried
canals

confused

Set 6: Different Places in the Philippines

WE FOUND THAT

In the Metro Manila dataset, it performs:

- **favorably** on narrow and separated roads
- **unfavorably** on wide roads or main highways
- **confused** on roofs of buildings and other infrastructures

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

favorably

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

unfavorably

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

Original Image

Predicted Mask

confused

Set 6: Different Places in the Philippines

WE FOUND THAT

In the Bohol dataset, it performs:

- **favorably** on roads with less curves
- **unfavorably** on zigzag roads
- **confused** on patches of land that resemble roads

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

favorably

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

Original Image					
Ground Truth					
Predicted Mask					

unfavorably

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

Original Image

Predicted Mask

confused

Set 6: Different Places in the Philippines

WE FOUND THAT

In the South Cotabato dataset, it performs:

- **favorably** on straight roads
- **unfavorably** on curved roads
- **confused** on boundaries of agricultural fields

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

Original Image

Ground Truth

Predicted Mask

favorably

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

Original Image

Ground Truth

Predicted Mask

unfavorably

Set 6:

Different Places in the Philippines

Original Image

Predicted Mask

confused

For Today

What is this study all about?

Methodology

Previous Studies

Results and Discussion

The Problem

Conclusions and Recommendations

6

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions and Recommendations

Our Findings demonstrate

An instance segmentation architecture like Mask R-CNN can be used to solve road segmentation problem by generalizing the object instances' masks.

In the future, this may ease and save time shifting from an instance segmentation to a general semantic segmentation problem.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Annotation is a significant input data.

Classified under Polygonal Annotation, Piece Annotation yielded better performance in terms of dice score and IoU and favorably on loss behavior than Whole and Segmented Annotation.

We further recommend

experimenting on other types of annotation other than polygonal, such as binary mask, lines and splines.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Higher image resolution and appropriate set of anchors relates to one another and affects the performance drastically.

If better performance is the priority than training and inference time, higher image resolution is better but if training and inference time were the priority, low image resolution with proper setting of anchors will help increase the performance.

Conclusions and Recommendations

We further recommend

incorporating anchor specific improvements such as approaches in:

- finding the appropriate anchor scales
- increasing the number of anchor scales considered
- optimizing anchors

Conclusions and Recommendations

Increasing the contrast in satellite images perform better than combining them to multi-directional hillshaded LiDAR images.

We further recommend

- exploring other ways of combining different data
- using other imageries

to combat road segmentation specific difficulties.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Mean pixel value of a larger dataset, like ImageNet, yields better performance than using our dataset's mean pixel value.

We further recommend

- exploring other mean pixel values from other larger datasets
- experimenting on other approaches for data preprocessing other than mean pixel subtraction

Conclusions and Recommendations

Using deeper residual networks produces better performance.

We further recommend

- implementing more layers of ResNet such as ResNet-152
- and other possible backbones such as VGGNet and AlexNet.

Challenges may include:

- changing some code for the FPN graph
- finding available weights for transfer learning or even taking up time if training from scratch.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Our model showed potential in segmenting roads of other areas with specific topographies.

Its performance in Bohol and South Cotabato datasets is impressive since it surpassed the original dataset's result. The Manila dataset is worse but it only lagged a few scores.

We further recommend

- adding more images to the dataset, either from Ilocos Norte or other areas, since in this study, Ilocos Norte dataset has a mixed topography, it only has a bit of each topography

Conclusions and Recommendations

Overall, we recommend

- further tuning such as in learning rates, gradient clip norms, and other tunable knobs of Mask R-CNN
- investigating other loss functions
 - for example in mask loss function, dice coefficient loss function or weighted binary cross entropy and dice coefficient loss helped increase performance in some implementations.
- post-processing the images
- Trying out other region-based models.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Overall, we recommend

- Comparing to the usual architectures/common architectures from road segmentation competitions and other newly released approach like PointRend of Facebook!!

PointRend: Image Segmentation as Rendering
Alexander Kirillov, Yuxin Wu, Kaiming He, Ross Girshick

Conclusions and Recommendations

Taken altogether,

Problems can be approached in different perspectives found inside and outside the toolbox – each of which have their own challenges.

Thank You

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Set 1:

Annotations and Augmentations

Loss Behavior

Overall Losses

Loss Behavior

RPN Bounding Box Losses

Loss Behavior

(a) Whole

(b) Segmented

(c) Piece

RPN Class Losses

Set 1:

Annotations and Augmentations

Loss Behavior

(a) Whole

(b) Segmented

(c) Piece

Mask R-CNN Bounding Box Losses

Set 1:

Annotations and Augmentations

Loss Behavior

Mask R-CNN Class Losses

Set 1:

Annotations and Augmentations

Loss Behavior

Mask R-CNN Mask Losses

Set 1: Annotations and Augmentations

Comparison with Binary Mask Annotation

Binary Mask

Whole

Segmented

Piece

